

MUHANDISLIK

& IQTISODIYOT

№12

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

2025 dekabr

Milliy nashrlar

OAK: <https://oak.uz/pages/4802>

05.00.00 - Texnika fanlari
08.00.00 - Iqtisodiyot fanlar

Google Scholar

OPEN ACCESS

ULRICHSWEB[®]
GLOBAL SERIALS DIRECTORY

Academic Resource Index
ResearchBib

ISSN INTERNATIONAL STANDARD SERIAL NUMBER INTERNATIONAL CENTRE

CYBERLENINKA

OpenAIRE

ROAD

INDEX COPERNICUS INTERNATIONAL

BASE

Crossref

НАУЧНАЯ ЭЛЕКТРОННАЯ БИБЛИОТЕКА LIBRARY.RU

ISSN: 3060-463X

РЭУ.РФ
РОССИЙСКИЙ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЙ УНИВЕРСИТЕТ
ИМЕНИ Г.В. ПЛЕХАНОВА
ТАШКЕНТСКИЙ ФИЛИАЛ

muhandislik **& iqtisodiyot**

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

Elektron nashr, 950 sahifa.
2025-yil, dekabr

Bosh muharrir:

Zokirova Nodira Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, DSc, professor

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Shakarov Zafar G'afrovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, PhD, dotsent

Tahrir hay'ati:

Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'z FA akademigi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Sharipov Kongratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori, professor

Maxkamov Baxtiyor Shuxratovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Shaumarov Said Sanatovich, texnika fanlari doktori, professor

Turayev Bahodir Xatamovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Nasimov Dilmurod Abdulloyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Allayeva Gulchexra Jalgasovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Arabov Nurali Uralovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Maxmudov Odiljon Xolmirzayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Xamrayeva Sayyora Nasimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Bobonazarova Jamila Xolmurodovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Irmatova Aziza Baxromovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Bo'taboyev Mahammadjon To'ychiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Shamshiyeva Nargizaxon Nosirxuja kizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor,

Xolmuxamedov Muhsinjon Murodullayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Xodjayeva Nodiraxon Abdurashidovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Amanov Otabek Amankulovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Qurbonov Samandar Pulatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Zikriyoyev Aziz Sadulloyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Tabayev Azamat Zaripbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sxay Lana Aleksandrovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Ismoilova Gulnora Fayzullayevna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Djumaniyazov Umrbek Ilxamovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Kasimova Nargiza Sabitdjanovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Kalanova Moxigul Baxritdinovna, dotsent

Ashurzoda Luiza Muxtarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sharipov Sardor Begmaxmat o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sharipov Botirali Roxataliyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor

Tursunov Ulug'bek Sativoldiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Bauyetdinov Majit Janizaqovich, Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti dotsenti, PhD

Botirov Bozorbek Musurmon o'g'li, Texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sultonov Shavkatjon Abdullayevich, Kimyo fanlari doktori, (DSc)

Jo'raeva Malohat Muhammadovna, filologiya fanlari doktori (DSc), professor.

Yusupov Maxamadamin Abduxamidovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (DSc), professor

Kalonova Moxigul Baxritdinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent

Mirzayev Kulmamat Djanzakovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (DSc), professor.

Karimova Nilufar Sadirdin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

muhandislik & iqtisodiyot

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

- 05.01.00 – Axborot texnologiyalari, boshqaruv va kompyuter grafikasi
- 05.01.01 – Muhandislik geometriyasi va kompyuter grafikasi. Audio va video texnologiyalari
- 05.01.02 – Tizimli tahlil, boshqaruv va axborotni qayta ishlash
- 05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
- 05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
- 05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
- 05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
- 05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
- 05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
- 05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
- 05.02.08 – Yer usti majmualari va uchish apparatlari
- 05.03.02 – Metrologiya va metrologiya ta'minoti
- 05.04.01 – Telekommunikatsiya va kompyuter tizimlari, telekommunikatsiya tarmoqlari va qurilmalari. Axborotlarni taqsimlash
- 05.05.03 – Yorug'lik texnikasi. Maxsus yoritish texnologiyasi
- 05.05.05 – Issiqlik texnikasining nazariy asoslari
- 05.05.06 – Qayta tiklanadigan energiya turlari asosidagi energiya qurilmalari
- 05.06.01 – To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat ishlab chiqarishlari materialshunosligi
- 05.08.03 – Temir yo'l transportini ishlatish
- 05.09.01 – Qurilish konstruksiyalari, bino va inshootlar
- 05.09.04 – Suv ta'minoti. Kanalizatsiya. Suv havzalarini muhofazalovchi qurilish tizimlari
- 10.00.06 – Qiyosiy adabiyotshunoslik, chog'ishtirma tilshunoslik va tarjimashunoslik
- 10.00.04 – Yevropa, Amerika va Avstraliya xalqlari tili va adabiyoti
- 08.00.01 – Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 – Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 – Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 – Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 – Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 – Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 – Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 – Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 – Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 – Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 – Marketing
- 08.00.12 – Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 – Menejment
- 08.00.14 – Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 – Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 – Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 – Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Ma'lumot uchun, OAK
Rayosatining 2024-yil 28-avgustdagi 360/5-son qarori bilan "Dissertatsiyalar asosiy ilmiy natijalarini chop etishga tavsiya etilgan milliy ilmiy nashrlar ro'yxati"ga texnika va iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha "Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali ro'yxatga kiritilgan.

Muassis: "Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz:

1. Toshkent shahridagi G.V.Plexanov nomidagi Rossiya iqtisodiyot universiteti
2. Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti
3. Toshkent irrigatsiya va qishloq xo'jaligini mexanizatsiyalash muhandislari instituti" milliy tadqiqot universiteti
4. Islom Karimov nomidagi Toshkent davlat texnika universiteti
5. Muhammad al-Xorazmiy nomidagi Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari universiteti
6. Toshkent davlat transport universiteti
7. Toshkent arxitektura-qurilish universiteti
8. Toshkent kimyo-texnologiya universiteti
9. Jizzax politexnika instituti

MUNDARIJA

RASMIY RIVOJLANISH YORDAMI (OFFICIAL DEVELOPMENT ASSISTANCE, ODA) ORQALI O'ZBEKISTONDA DAVLAT MOLIYASINI BOSHQARISH (PUBLIC FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT, PFM) TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	24
Pulatov Dilshod Haqberdiyevich, Ulug'ova Maftunabonu To'iqinovna	
INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN LEADING WHEAT-PRODUCING COUNTRIES.....	28
Turayeva Gulizahro	
BLOKCHEYN TIZIMLARI UCHUN XESH FUNKSIYALARNI TANLASH MEZONLARI VA SAMARADORLIK KO'RSATKICHLARI TAHLILI	32
Abduraximov Baxtiyor, Allanov Orif, Turdibekov Baxtiyor	
RIVOJLANGAN DAVLATLAR TAJRIBASI ASOSIDA KICHIK KORXONALARDA ISHLAB CHIQARISHNI SAMARALI TASHKIL ETISH MODELLARI: NAMANGAN VILOYATI MISOLIDA	39
Xonto'rayev Obbosxon Kamolxon o'g'li	
ISSIQLIK AKKUMULYATORINING RAZRYADLANISH JARAYONIDA SUYUQLIK QATLAMLARIDA HARORAT TAQSIMLANISHINING BIR O'LCHOVLI MODEL I.....	43
B.A. Hikmatov, M.S. Mirzayev	
ISLOM MOLIYASI TAMOYILLARI ASOSIDA YASHIL LOYIHALARNI MOLIYALASHTIRISH IMKONIYATLARI.....	49
Safarova Nasiba Gulmurod qizi	
ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТУАЛЬНЫХ СИСТЕМ В ОБУЧЕНИИ СПЕЦИАЛИСТОВ ПО ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫМ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯМ.....	54
Даниярова Улбосын Куатбаевна	
YANGI TURDAGI IKKI QATLAMLI TRIKOTAJ TO'QIMALARI KO'RSATKICHLARINI KOMPLEKS BAHOLASH	58
Ergasheva Rashida Abdug'aniyevna	
HALQALI YIGIRISH MASHINASIDA BURAM UCHBURCHAGINING IP UZILISHIGA BOG'LIQLIGINI TADQIQI.....	62
Soliyev Azizbek Kamoldinovich	
НОВЫЕ ТЕНДЕНЦИИ ТУРИЗМА 2030: СТРАТЕГИЧЕСКИЕ ОРИЕНТИРЫ И РЕКОМЕНДАЦИИ ДЛЯ УЗБЕКИСТАНА	69
Гольшева Елена Вячеславовна	
STRATEGIK JARAYONNING MODELLARI	76
Musayeva Dilnoza Dilshatovna	
МАТЕМАТИЧЕСКИЕ МОДЕЛИ ОЦЕНКИ СТОИМОСТИ КВАРТИР В МНОГОЭТАЖНЫХ ДОМАХ.....	81
Уринов Адхамжон Акбарович	
MATERIALLARNI MURAKKAB YASSI TRAEKTORIYALAR BO'YICHA DEFORMASIYALANTIRISHDA PLASTIK DEFORMASIYALANISH JARAYONLARI	88
A.Xakimov, X.Xakimov	
TIJORAT BANKLARI TOMONIDAN LOYIHALARNI ISLOM MOLIYA INSTRUMENTLARI ORQALI MOLIYALASHTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	95
Xaitov Shaxzod Sharipboyevich	
SANOAT KORXONALARINING RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH CHORA-TADBIRLARINING KETMA KETLIGI	102
Xusanova Maloxat Mengnorovna	
TO'QIMACHILIK KORXONALARIDA LOGISTIKA XARAJATLARI TAHLILI	107
Saidova Kamola Xoshimovna	

OZIQ-OVQAT SANOATINI IQTISODIY RIVOJLANTIRISHDA EKOLOGIK MUAMMOLAR VA ULARNI YECHISHNING METODOLOGIK YONDASHUVLARI	111
Tleuv Niyetulla Raxmanovich	
YUQORI MUSTAHKAM KOMPOZIT ARMATURALARDAN FOYDALANILGAN TEMIRBETON KONSTRUKSIYALARINING YUK KO'TARUVCHANLIGI VA UZOQ MUDDATLI DEFORMATSIYALARINI BAHOLASH	114
Mamajanova Odina Alisher qizi	
KORXONALARDA DAROMADLILIK KO'RSATKICHLARINI BAHOLASHNING ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLARI	119
Farog'at Xo'jabekova, Eshankulova Nafisa Komiljon qizi	
TEMIR YO'L INFRATUZILMASIDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOT TAMOYILLARINI QO'LLASH: CSR, ESG VA PRI ASOSIDA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH STRATEGIYASINI SHAKLLANTIRISH	124
Abduraxmanova Muqaddas Toxtasinovna	
THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN OPTIMIZING MARKETING AND EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES IN HIGHER EDUCATION	128
Sadikov Shoxrux Shuhratovich	
BANK FAOLIYATIDA "YASHIL" MOLIYAVIY VOSITALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	133
Abduraxmonov Alimardon Sodiq o'g'li	
TIJORAT BANKLARI TOMONIDAN LOYIHALARNI ISLOM MOLIYA INSTRUMENTLARI ORQALI MOLIYALASHTIRISH YO'LLARI	139
Xaitov Shaxzod Sharipboyevich	
BOSHQARUV PSIXOLOGIYASIGA DOIR MUAMMOLARNI BARTARAF ETISHNING ZAMONAVIY YO'NALISHLARI	145
Aripov Oybek Abdullayevich	
TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARIDA INNOVATSIYALARNI JORIY ETISHNING IQTISODIY SAMARALARI	150
Karimov Nodirbek	
УТИЛИЗАЦИЯ ПОБОЧНЫХ ПРОДУКТОВ ПЕРЕРАБОТКИ ХЛОПКА ДЛЯ СИНТЕЗА АНТИКОРРОЗИОННЫХ КОМПОЗИЦИОННЫХ ПОКРЫТИЙ.....	155
Ситмуратов Тулкинбек Сабирбаевич, Баходиров Худайберган Баходир угли	
SANOAT KORXONALARIDA MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIKNI TA'MINLASHNING METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI.....	163
Ergashev Muhibbek Aslam o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATIDA XORIJIY INVESTITSIYALAR SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	168
Nazarova A.N.	
АВТОМАТИЗИРОВАННАЯ СИСТЕМА РАСЧЁТА ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ СОТРУДНИКОВ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ	172
Шухратов Мамуржон Шухрат угли	
BLOCKCHIAN, IOT (INTERNET OF THINGS) NING IQTISODIY SOHALARDA QO'LLANISHI	178
Avazov Ergash Xidirberdiyevich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA INVESTITSIYALARNI MOLIYAVIY BOSHQARISHNING JORIY HOLATI VA EKONOMETRIK TAHLILLAR ASOSIDA KELGUSI YILLAR PROGNOZI.....	182
Ismailov Dilshod Anvarjonovich	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI KLASTERLARI MOLIYAVIY HOLATINING NAZARIY JIHATLARI	190
Dildora Yuldasheva	
TURIZM SOHASIDA TRANSPORT XIZMATLARINING HOLATI	194
Xalimov Shaxboz Xalimovich	
MAHALLA BUDJETI VA SOLIQLARNING YIG'ILUVCHANLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI	200
Abdullayev Zafarbek Safibullayevich	

BUDJET TASHKILOTLARIDA QURILISH-TA'MIRLASH XARAJATLARI HISOBINING USLUBIY JIHATLARI.....	206
<i>Azizova Zilola Lochinovna</i>	
KOSHI – BUNYAKOVSKIY – SHVARS INTEGRAL TENGSIZLIGI VA UNING IQTISODIYOTDAGI ROLI.....	212
<i>Saipnazarov Shaylovbek Aktamovich</i>	
ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ ПРИНЦИПОВ ЦИРКУЛЯРНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ В АГРОПРОДОВОЛЬСТВЕННЫЙ СЕКТОР УЗБЕКИСТАНА: ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКАЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ, ПЕРЕРАБОТКА БИОМАССЫ И СТРАТЕГИИ СОКРАЩЕНИЯ ПОСТУБОРОЧНЫХ ПОТЕРЬ	219
<i>Эгамбердиев Хумоюн Хамрокулович</i>	
HOVUZ BALIQCHILIGI XO'JALIKLARIDA REJALASHTIRISHNING MUDDATLARI VA BOSQICHLARI	227
<i>Dosmuratova Shaxista Kengashovna, Menglikulov Bakhtiyor Yusupovich</i>	
O'ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA KICHIK BIZNESNI QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASH TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI	233
<i>Ergashev Jamshid Jamoliddinovich</i>	
KON-METALLURGIYA KORXONALARINING KORPORATIV BOSHQARUV TIZIMIDA KPINING O'RNI VA AHAMIYATI.....	237
<i>Ergashov Botirjon Ergashovich</i>	
SANOAT KORXONALARIDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARNI JORIY ETISHNING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI.....	245
<i>Ahmadjanov Ilyosbek</i>	
ACCELERATING SOCIOECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN RURAL AREAS THROUGH DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS	250
<i>O.Q. Xudayberdiyeva, Z.B. Negmatullayeva</i>	
ISSIQXONALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING OZIQ-OVQAT XAVFSIZLIGIGA TA'SIRI BO'YICHA MUAMMONI ASOSLASH VA UNING MILLIY MANFAATLARGA ALOQADORLIGINI ANIQLASH	256
<i>Otavullaev Sukhrob Sa'dullo o'g'li</i>	
NAMANGAN VILOYATIDA DON MAHSULOTLARI NARXLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA BOZOR TAJRIBASI	260
<i>Bahriddinov Jahongirbek Ravshanjon o'g'li</i>	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISHNING JAHON TAJRIBASI: MUAMMO VA ISTIQBOL	264
<i>Mamadaliyev Akmaljon</i>	
ПОВЫШЕНИЕ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ ЗНАЧИМОСТИ НАЛОГОВ В НОВОЙ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ СИТУАЦИИ.....	269
<i>Зайналов Джахонгир Расулович</i>	
FARG'ONA VODIYSIDA KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARI FAOLIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING HUDUDIY XUSUSIYATLARI	274
<i>Murodxiyeva Feruza Majidovna</i>	
TOG' VA TOG'OLDI HUDUDLARIDA IQLIM O'ZGARISHI SHAROITIDA QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASH STRATEGIYALARI.....	280
<i>Abdulxayeva Gulshan Maxmudovna</i>	
LABOR MIGRATION IN UZBEKISTAN: SOCIO-ECONOMIC TRENDS AND DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS	285
<i>Razakova Barno Sayfiyeva</i>	
U-NET BASED POLYP SEGMENTATION ON KVASIR-SEG DATASET: PERFORMANCE EVALUATION AND COMPARISON WITH STATE-OF-THE-ART METHODS	289
<i>Mukhriddin Arabboev, Shohruh Begmatov, Sukhrob Bobojanov</i>	

IQTISODIYOT TARMOQLARI VA SOHALARI RIVOJLANISHIDA SUN'YI INTELLEKTDAN FOYDALANISH MASALALARI	300
<i>Davletov Islambek Xalikovich, Normirzayev Ulmasjon Muzaffarjon o'g'li</i>	
IQTISODIYOTDA SAMARALI RAQOBAT MUHITINI SHAKLLANTIRISH SHART-SHAROITLARI VA OMILLARI	304
<i>Karimova Iroda Abdusattarovna</i>	
"MENING MAKTABIM" LOYIHASINI OMMALASHTIRISH BO'YICHA XORIJIY MAMLAKATLAR TAJRIBASI	311
<i>Diilshod Pulatov, Xamidaxon Akbarova, Dildora Mirzayeva</i>	
ISSUES OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN THE EDUCATION MARKET	320
<i>Inomiddin Imomov</i>	
СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ МЕТОДА ОЦЕНКИ ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ С УЧЕТОМ СТЕПЕНИ НОВИЗНЫ И ЭФФЕКТОВ	324
<i>Алиева Эльнара Аметовна</i>	
ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ ЦИФРОВЫХ БИЗНЕС-МОДЕЛЕЙ В СИСТЕМУ КОНКУРЕНТНЫХ ПРЕИМУЩЕСТВ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	331
<i>Назарова Гулчехра Нурмуханбетовна</i>	
ECONOMIC GROWTH: THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL ASPECT	336
<i>Bustonov Mansurjon Mardonakulovich</i>	
AGROKLASTERDAGI XO'JALIK YURITUVCHI SUBYEKTLAR O'RTASIDAGI O'ZARO ALOQALAR MEKANIZMINING BUGUNGI HOLATI	342
<i>Xaydarov Sardor Komil o'g'li</i>	
SIMSIZ ALOQA TEXNOLOGIYALARI YORDAMIDA TEMIR YO'L STANSIYALARIDA POYEZDLAR HARAKATINI TASHKIL ETISH	350
<i>Joniqulov Egamberdi Shavkat o'g'li</i>	
GENDER SIYOSATI VA DEMOGRAFIK O'SISHNING INSON KAPITALIGA TA'SIRI	357
<i>Ruzmetova Gulira'no Atabekovna</i>	
СОСТОЯНИЕ ВИТАМИННО-МИНЕРАЛЬНОГО ОБМЕНА (ВИТАМИН D, КАЛЬЦИЙ, МАГНИЙ, ФОСФОР) У ДЕТЕЙ РАННЕГО ВОЗРАСТА С ОСТРОЙ ПНЕВМОНИЕЙ НА ФОНЕ ВЕГЕТАТИВНЫХ ДИСФУНКЦИЙ	364
<i>Абдурахмонов Жасур Нематович, Шарипова Олия Аскарровна, Бахронов Шерзод Самиевич</i>	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNING MOHIYATI VA TARKIBIY TUZILISHI	373
<i>Kalandarova Elnura Muzaffar qizi</i>	
ОСНОВНЫЕ НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ ОЦЕНКИ ФИНАНСОВОЙ УСТОЙЧИВОСТИ АО ХУДУДГАЗТАЪМИНОТ	377
<i>Хусанов Дурбек Нишанович</i>	
ТЕМИР YO'L TRANSPORTIDA NAZORAT GABARIT QURILMALARINING ZAMONAVIY HOLATI, TAHLILI VA HARAKAT TAKRIBI GABARITLARINI ANIQLASH USULINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	384
<i>Xidirov Erkin Irgashovich</i>	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA SUV RESURSLARIDAN FOYDALANISH VA SAMARALI TAQSIMLASHDA RIVOJLANGAN XORIJIY MAMLAKATLAR TAJRIBALARI	391
<i>Amanbaev Amanali Ortazbaevich</i>	
GLOBAL DARAJADA FAOLIYAT YURITADIGAN BRONLASH TIZIMLARINING ILG'OR XORIY TAJRIBALARI	396
<i>Ismatillaeva Sitara Sayfidin qizi</i>	
DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIGI ASOSIDA INFRATUZILMA LOYIHALARNI MOLiyALASHTIRISHNING NORMATIV-HUQUQIY ASOSLARI	403
<i>Akmal Shodiyev</i>	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI MAHSULOTLARI ISHLAB CHIQRUVCHI KORXONALARDA LIZING MUNOSABATLARI HISOBI	408
<i>Inamov Abdusalom Muhammadovich, Inomov Sardor Abdusalomovich, Inomov Hasanboy Abdusalom o'g'li</i>	

O'TKIR BRONXOLIOT BILAN KASALLANGAN BOLALARDA KATAMNEZNING EKOLOGIK OMILLAR TA'SIRIDA UZIGA XOS KECHISHI.....	412
Azimova Kamola Talatovna	
THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF STUDYING CONCEPTS RELATED TO YOUTH TOURISM.....	416
Norbojev Allayor Ismoilovich, Mansurova Zebuniso Abdurashidovna	
THE ESSENTIAL STRATEGIES WAYS OF SERICULTURE INDUSTRY OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN.....	420
Khojimatov Ravshanbek Rasuljonovich	
BLENDED LEARNING PLATFORMASI KANSEPSIYASI, ARXITEKTURASI VA FUNKSIONAL TUZILMASI.....	425
Qobulova Madina Tuxbatillo qizi, Mirzaaxmedov Muxammadbobur Karimberdiyevich	
ASALARICHILIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING AHOLI DAROMADLARI VA FAROVONLIGIGA TA'SIRI: IQTISODIY TAHLIL VA EKONOMETRIK BAHOLASH.....	430
Kuanishbay Berdimuratov	
MARKETING EKOTIZIMINI SHAKLLANTIRISHGA OID XORIJIY YONDASHUVLAR TAHLILI.....	434
Sobirov Azizbek Avazbekovich	
УЧЕТНО-АНАЛИТИЧЕСКОЕ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЕ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ДЕНЕЖНЫМИ ПОТОКАМИ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ.....	443
Бабахонов Бабуржон Шухрат угли	
KICHIK BIZNES SUBYEKTLARIGA SOLIQ IMTIYOZLARINI QO'LLASH MASALALARI.....	449
Ibroximov Muxammadjon Abdullajanovich	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA LOGISTIKA BOSHQARUVINING RAQAMLI MODEL VA UNING SAMARADORLIGI.....	453
Olimova Bahora Shuxratovna	
СУЩНОСТЬ И ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЕ СОДЕРЖАНИЕ ФИНАНСОВЫХ РЕЗУЛЬТАТОВ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯ.....	463
Муминходжаева Дилноза Рамизовна	
ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ФИНАНСОВЫМИ РИСКАМИ В СЕЛЬСКОМ ХОЗЯЙСТВЕ НА ОСНОВЕ ЦИФРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ И АНАЛИТИЧЕСКИХ ПЛАТФОРМ.....	468
Дурманов Акмал Шаймарданович	
УПРАВЛЕНИЕ ИННОВАЦИОННЫМ РАЗВИТИЕМ СОЦИАЛЬНОГО СЕКТОРА ЭКОНОМИКИ: ВЫЗОВЫ И НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ РЕФОРМ В СФЕРЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ И ЗДРАВООХРАНЕНИЯ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	477
Холмуратов Джохонгир Салимбек угли	
O'ZBEKISTONDA XORIJIY INVESTITSIYALARNI JALB ETISHDA TIJORAT BANKLARINING ROLI.....	483
Yuldashev Erkin Xusanovich	
MINTAQAVIY INVESTITSIYA-INNOVASION JARAYONLARGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR.....	489
Xamrayev Quvvat Iskandarovich	
AGROKLAFTERLARDA ICHKI SOTISH JARAYONIDA TRANSFERT BAHOLARNI BELGILASH USULLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	495
Eshmuradov Ulug'bek Tashmuratovich	
INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF MICE TOURISM AND ITS ADAPTATION TO THE CONDITIONS OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN.....	501
Ilkhomova Gulnoza Zayniddin kizi	
MUHANDISLIK KONSTRUKSIYALARIDA MURAKKAB SIRTLARNI CHIZMA GEOMETRIYA YORDAMIDA TAHLIL QILISH.....	507
Qutbtiddinov Hikmatillo Quدراتillo o'g'li	
TADBIRKORLIKNI QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASHNING ZAMONAVIY MEXANIZMLARI VA ULARNING IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHGA TA'SIRI.....	512
Umarova Munira Muxitdinovna	

JINDA ARRALI SILINDR TISHLARIDAN TOLANI AJRATISH JARAYONINI HAVO OQIMI ASOSIDA OPTIMALLASHTIRUVCHI ENERGIYA TEJAMKOR QURILMANI MODELLASHTIRISH.....	516
Mirzakarimov Mirsharofiddin Mirzaabdurahimovich	
TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARI TOMONIDAN ISHLAB CHIQRILGAN MAHSULOTLARNI XORIJGA EKSPORT QILISH MEKANIZMLARI	524
Matkarimov Anvar Tajimatovich	
MUHANDISLIK KONSTRUKSIYALARIDA MURAKKAB SIRTLARNI CHIZMA GEOMETRIYA YORDAMIDA TAHLIL QILISH.....	528
Qutbtiddinov Hikmatillo Qudratillo o'g'li	
SOLIQ TO'LOVCHILAR FAOLIYATINI SOLIQ NAZORATINI AMALGA OSHIRISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI	533
Ismailov Bobir Salomovich	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIK KORXONALARIDA KAPITAL QO'YILMALAR XUSUSIYATLARI VA ULAR AUDITINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	540
Baxriyev Muxiddin Sheraliyevich	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIK KORXONALARIDA ASOSIY VOSITALAR VA ULAR BUXGALTERIYA HISOBINING XUSUSIYATLARI.....	545
Fayzullayev Murodjon Nematulayevich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA KLASTER IQTISODIYOTI: INVESTITSIYALAR, EKSPORT VA SANOAT ISHLAB CHIQRISHINING ZAMONAVIY TENDENSIYALARI (2022-2024-YILLAR KESIMIDA).....	550
O'rinboyev Ulug'bek Otabekovich, Jabbarov Majidbek Erzodovich, Ruzmetova Gulira'no Atabekovna	
GLOBAL YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASINI SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASHDA EKOLOGIK, IJTIMOY-IQTISODIY OMILLARNING TAHLILI	556
M.M.Muminova	
RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA VA SMART TURIZM SHAROITIDA TURIZM INFRATUZILMASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING XORIJIY TAJRIBASI VA O'ZBEKISTON ISTIQBOLLARI	565
Najmidinov Azizbek Bahrom o'g'li	
ТЕКУЩИЕ УГРОЗЫ И ВЫЗОВЫ, СВЯЗАННЫЕ С МИГРАЦИОННЫМИ КРИЗИСАМИ	571
Бегматов Хусанбек	
ELEKTRON TIJORAT SEKTORI UCHUN ONLAYN REKLAMA SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH	575
Rajabova Dilbar Ixtiyor qizi	
RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA O'ZBEKISTON MEVA-SABZAVOTCHILIK SOHASIDA MAHSULOT YETISHTIRISHDAN TORTIB UNI BOZORGA CHIQRISHGACHA BO'LGAN JARAYONDA NEYROMARKETING TEXNOLOGIYALARINI QO'LLASHNING NAZARIY VA AMALIY JIHATLARI	582
Sadiy Shukrillo Asatillo o'g'li	
YOSH TADBIRKORLAR FAOLIYATIDA INNOVATSION G'OYALARNING AMALIY AHAMIYATI	590
Ergashev Oybek Xaydaraliyevich	
ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ НЕТРАДИЦИОННОГО СБАЛАНСИРОВАННОГО КОМБИКОРМА, С ОБОГАЩЕННЫМ БЕЛКОМ И ФЕРМЕНТАМИ СОСТАВОМ ИЗ ГРИБКА PLEUROTUS OSTREATUS.....	594
Ниёзов Хусан Ниёз угли	
MINTAQAVIY RIVOJLANISH INDIKATOR TIZIMINING AHAMIYATI	601
Turdiyev Ulug'bek Qayumovich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA EKSPORTNI RAG'BATLANTIRISH BO'YICHA DAVLAT SIYOSATI	608
Abdug'aniyev Murodjon Shavkat o'g'li	
TO'QIMACHILIK KORXONALARINING RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI BOSHQARISH JARAYONI VA TIZIMI	612
Xonkeldiyeva Komilaxon Ravshanjon qizi	

SPORT SANOATINING INNOVATSION RIVOJLANISHIGA OID XORIJIY TAJRIBALAR TAHLILI.....	616
Xamraqulov Ixtiyor Baxtiyorovich	
MARKAZLASHTIRILGAN DISPATCHERLIK TIZIMIDA POEZDLAR HARAKATI XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA AVTOMATLAR NAZARIYASIGA ASOSLANGAN INTEGRATSIYALASHGAN MATEMATIK MODEL.....	620
Muhiddinov Obidjon Omonjon o'g'li	
ПРОЦЕНТНЫЙ РИСК ПО КРЕДИТАМ: АНАЛИЗ, ОЦЕНКА И УПРАВЛЕНИЕ.....	627
Абдуллаев Шахобиддин Шамсиддинович	
REDUCTION OF GREENHOUSE GAS EMISSIONS: EMISSION QUOTAS OR MANDATORY CONTROL TECHNOLOGIES.....	633
Bobonov Doston Abdumo'min o'g'li, Qozoqboyev Jasur Abduvali o'g'li	
AYOLLAR TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATINI BAHOLASH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH (NAMANGAN VILOYATI MISOLIDA).....	637
Raximova Moxigul Isroiljonovna	
ПОЛУЧЕНИЕ СТОМАТОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ЦЕМЕНТА С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ ВОЗОБНОВЛЯЕМЫХ ИСТОЧНИКОВ ЭНЕРГИИ.....	643
Арипова Мастура Хикматовна, Ташбаев Джахангир Назим угли	
МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЕ ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫХ ГОРЕЛОК И ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ИХ ТЕПЛОВОЙ НАГРУЗКИ.....	652
Ражабов Азамат Тоирович	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIK TEXNIKALARI MARKETINGI VA UNING SAMARADORLIK KO'RSATKICHLARI.....	658
Xolmirzayev Bobur Mansurovich	
ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ СУБСИДИАРНОЙ ОТВЕТСТВЕННОСТИ НА ДОСУДЕБНОЙ СТАДИИ АНКРОТСТВА: ЗАРУБЕЖНЫЙ ОПЫТ И ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ВНЕДРЕНИЯ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	663
Хамзина Динара Рашатовна	
YASHIL REKREATSION TURIZM KONSEPSIYASINI JORIY ETISHNING ILMIIY-AMALIY JIHATLARI.....	669
Baxriyeva Zarina Nasimovna	
KORXONALARDA DIVERSIFIKATSIYA SIYOSATINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA IQTISODIY MEKANIZMLARINING O'RNI.....	672
Mirzarayimova Feruza Zokirjon qizi, Levakov Izzatulla Nematillayevich	
QALINLIGI 2 MM BO'LGAN TASMALI LISTLARNI SOVUQ HOLATDA PROKATLASH TEXNOLOGIK JARAYONINI ISHLAB CHIQISH.....	679
Yusupov Abdulaziz Abdullajanovich, Saydumarov Botir Muradovich, Arslonov Asadbek G'aybulla o'g'li	
HUDUDIY TARMOQLANGAN AVTOMOBIL YO'LLARI MUHANDISLIK INSHOOTLARI KOMPLEKSINI LOYIHALASH VA QURISH JARAYONLARINI MODELLASHTIRISH.....	682
Zikrayev Akmaljon Alimovich	
TIJORAT BANKLARI FAOLIYATIDA DAROMADLARNI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI.....	688
Ostonaqulova Gulchehraxon Muhammadyoqub qizi	
"MIKROSIMULYATSION MODELLAR" VA ULAR YORDAMIDA IQTISODIY SIYOSATGA OID QARORLARNING TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARIGA TA'SIRINI BAHOLASHDAGI AHAMIYATI.....	694
Mualliflar Pulatov Dilshod Xaqberdiyevich, Raxmonov Doniyor Ixtiyorjon o'g'li, Ortiqova Niginabonu Alisher qizi, Raxmonov Jo'rabek Hamroyevich	
MINTAQADA SANOAT KORXONALARI TUZILMAVIY KO'RSATKICHLAR TIZIMI VA TAMOIYILLARI.....	702
Jabborov Elbek Erkin o'g'li	
MOLIYAVIY REJALASHTIRISH VA TARTIBGA SOLISH.....	707
Sharoxmatov Abduraxim Abdulamitovich	

SMART SOATLAR YORDAMIDA BEMORLAR SALOMATLIGINI NAZORAT QILISH.....	712
<i>Alimqulov Nurmuhammad Muqumjon o'g'li, Eraliyev Humoyun Ma'mirjon o'g'li, Madaminova Mahliyo Bahodirjon qizi</i>	
PENSIYA JAMG'ARMASI FAOLIYATINI TARTIBGA SOLISHDA DAVLATNING ROLI	718
<i>Sherjonov Doniyor Sapparbayevich</i>	
TOG'-KON SANOATI KORXONALARIDA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH IMKONIYATLARINI BAHOLASH.....	722
<i>Karimov Ma'ruf Ixtiyorovich</i>	
MINTAQA IQTISODIYOTINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA ISLOM MOLIVASINING AHAMIYATI	726
<i>Sultonov Baxtiyor Baxodirovich</i>	
UCH FAZALI IKKI CHULG'AMLI MOYLI TRANSFORMATORLARNING ISSIQLIK HISOBINI MODELLASHTIRISH VA TADQIQ QILISH	731
<i>Taniyev Mirzoxid Xurramovich, Bekishev Allabergen Yergashevich, Omonboyev Dilrux Nuraddin o'g'li</i>	
ERKIN IQTISODIY ZONALARNING RIVOJLANISHI BOSQICHLARI	736
<i>Mamadiyev Elyor Akmalovich, Sharipov K. A.</i>	
MOLIYAVIY INKLUZIVNING IJTIMOYIY TABAQALANISHGA TA'SIRINING NAZARIY JIHATLARI.....	740
<i>Adashaliyev Baxtiyorjon Valisher o'g'li</i>	
ВОПРОСЫ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ БУХГАЛТЕРСКОГО УЧЁТА ОСНОВНЫХ СРЕДСТВ К МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫМ СТАНДАРТАМ БУХГАЛТЕРСКОГО УЧЁТА	746
<i>Муҳидинов Аюббек Нуритдинович</i>	
РОЛЬ КОЛЛЕКТОРНО-ДРЕНАЖНЫХ СИСТЕМ В СЕЛЬСКОМ ХОЗЯЙСТВЕ	753
<i>Жангабаев Данияр Мансурович, Хожамуратова Роза Тажимуратовна</i>	
ASSESSMENT OF ESG INDICES OF PRESTIGIOUS HOTELS IN UZBEKISTAN	759
<i>Saidova Madina Xayrullo qizi</i>	
FISKAL SIYOSATDA MAHALLIY BUDJETLAR MUSTAQILLIGINI OSHIRISHNING MOLIVAVIY INSTRUMENTLARI	765
<i>Muxitdinov Sidikxo'ja Akobirxo'ja o'g'li</i>	
TRANSFORMATSIYALASH JARAYONIDA TIJORAT BANKLARI KREDITLASH AMALIYOTINING XORIIY TAJRIBASI.....	771
<i>Jabbarov Nodir Umirovich</i>	
AKSIZ SOLINISHNING IJTIMOYIY-IQTISODIY TA'SIRI	775
<i>Abdulxayeva Shaxnoza Muxammadiyevna</i>	
O'ZBEKISTONDA QISHLOQ XO'JALIGINING IQTISODIY-STATISTIK TAHLILI VA UNI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI	781
<i>Shavkat Djumaniyazov</i>	
EKISHDA CHIGITNI BIR XIL TARQATISH VA OPTIMALLASHTIRISH USULLARI.....	787
<i>Imomov Shavkat Jaxonovich, Nuritov Ikrom Rajabovich, Babamuradov Anvar Baxtiyorovich</i>	
KICHIK BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIKDA KOMPLEKS IQTISODIY TAHLIL TIZIMINI JORIY ETISH	790
<i>Akbarov Akramjon Ibroximjonovich</i>	
INNOVATION FAOLIYAT XARAJATLARINING BUXGALTYERIYA HISOBINI VA AUDITINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	793
<i>Mustafoev Akbar Mustafo o'g'li</i>	
INTELLIGENT SYSTEM FOR MONITORING AND MANAGEMENT OF THE VEGETABLE OIL REFINING PROCESS	798
<i>Ortiqov Elbek Elmirza o'g'li</i>	
O'ZBEKISTONDA KREATIV INDUSTRIYA VA EVENT-MENEJMENTNING HUQUQIY-ME'YORIY ASOSLARI.....	806
<i>Shaxabatdin Maxamatdinov Isak uli</i>	

РОЛЬ И РАЗВИТИЕ ТРАНСПОРТНОЙ ИНФРАСТРУКТУРЫ В ТОРГОВЫХ ОТНОШЕНИЯХ МЕЖДУ УЗБЕКИСТАНОМ И КИТАЕМ.....	812
Wang Jianhong, Норов Улугбек Ирискулович	
FARMATSEVTIKA KORXONALARIDA YORDAMCHI ISHLAB CHIQRISH JARAYONLARI HISOBI VA YORDAMCHI MAHSULOTLAR TANNARXINI ANIQLASHNING O'ZIGA XOS JIHATLARI	816
Xudaynazarova Dilnoza Gafurovna	
XO'JALIK YURITUVCHI SUBYEKTLARNING ASOSIY IQTISODIY KO'RSATKICHLARINI STRATEGIK BOSHQARUV HISOBI DOIRASIDA SHAKLLANTIRISH VA ULARNING HOLATINI TAHLIL QILISH	821
Hamroyeva Zuhra Amiral qizi	
К ВОПРОСУ РАСЧЕТА МОЩНОСТИ, НЕОБХОДИМОЙ ДЛЯ РАЗОГРЕВА КРОМОК ТРУБНОЙ ЗАГОТОВКИ ДО ТЕМПЕРАТУРЫ СВАРКИ	825
Заиркулов Элёр Ёкубжон ўғли	
TEKNOLOGIK JARAYONLARNI BOSHQARISHNING AVTOMATLASHTIRILGAN TIZIMLARI	830
Bekishev Allabergen Yergashevich, Hamadulloev Diyorbek Hasanboy o'g'li	
ESG (ENVIRONMENTAL, SOCIAL AND GOVERNANCE) TAMOYILLARINING IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISH VA KORPORATIV FAOLIYATGA TA'SIRI: MAKRO VA MIKRO DARAJADAGI TAHLIL	834
Murtozayev Sardorbek Abdijalil o'g'li	
TESTING THE STATISTICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF DYNAMIC MODELS IN ECONOMICS	838
Muradov Rustamjon Sobitkhonovich	
REAL IQTISODIY DAVRLAR NAZARIYASI VA UN DAN MAKROIQTISODIY TADQIQOTLARDA FOYDALANISH	843
Rustamov Narzillo Istamovich	
РАСЧЕТ РАСТЯЖЕНИЯ ДРЕВЕСИНЫ И ДЕРЕВЯННЫХ КОНСТРУКЦИЙ ИЗ МЕСТНЫХ ДРЕВЕСНЫХ МАТЕРИАЛОВ ПОД ДИНАМИЧЕСКИМИ НАГРУЗКАМИ.....	848
Юнусалиев Эльмурод Мухаммадьякубович, Ташпулатов Илхомжон Бахтиёрович	
ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИЯ КОРПОРАТИВНОГО УПРАВЛЕНИЯ И ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА КАК ФАКТОР РАЗВИТИЯ ФОНДОВОГО РЫНКА: МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ОПЫТ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ ДЛЯ УЗБЕКИСТАНА	854
Евгений Юрьевич Шек	
ЗАРУБЕЖНЫЙ ОПЫТ СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЯ ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫХ КЛАСТЕРОВ И ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ЕГО АДАПТАЦИИ В НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ.....	860
Шодмонов Қобилжон Қахрамон ўғли	
AGRAR IQTISODIYOTNI INNOVATSION RIVOJLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY-METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI.....	870
Ibrohimova Maqsuda Muhammadjon qizi, Ibrohimova Muazzam Muhammadjon qizi	
XORAZM VILOYATIDA KICHIK BIZNESNING EKSPORT SALOHİYATIDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH VA BU BORADAGI MUAMMOLAR.....	873
Raxmatullayev Umarbek Ulug'bekovich	
ДАТЧИКИ ИНТЕРНЕТА ВЕЩЕЙ И ИХ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ДЛЯ МОНИТОРИНГА ТЕПЛИЧНЫХ КОМПЛЕКСОВ	878
Самадов Эльёр Эркинович	
МЕТОДЫ ОПТИМИЗАЦИИ РАБОТЫ ЭКСКАВАТОРНО-АВТОМОБИЛЬНОГО КОМПЛЕКСА КАК ФАКТОР ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ПРОИЗВОДИТЕЛЬНОСТИ НА ОТКРЫТЫХ ГОРНЫХ РАБОТАХ	884
Аннакулов Тулкин Жовбекович, Норимонов Шамсиддин Нураддинович	
ПРОГНОЗИРУЮЩЕЕ УПРАВЛЕНИЕ СЛОЖНЫМИ ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКИМИ ПРОЦЕССАМИ И ПРОИЗВОДСТВАМИ НА ОСНОВЕ НЕЙРОННЫХ СЕТЕЙ	892
Гулямов Шухрат Манапович	

OLIY TA'LIM TASHKILOTI SUBYEKTLARIDA BUDJET MABLAG'LARI BO'YICHA XARAJATLAR HISOBINI YURITISH	896
<i>Xonimqulov Islom Ergash o'g'li</i>	
XIZMAT KO'RSATUVCHI TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARIDA MODDIY-TEXNIKA RESURSLARINI BOSHQARISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR	901
<i>Kamoliddinov Ilxomjon Muxammadjonovich</i>	
THE HIDE AND SHADOW ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN	905
<i>Koshanov Abdimurat Azat uli, Abdimuratova Altingul Kalbayevna</i>	
SHAHAR AGLOMERATSIYALARI FAOLIYATINI TAHLIL QILISH VA BAHOLASH.....	910
<i>Abdulxakimov Zuxrali Tursunaliyevich</i>	
MOL-MULK SOLIG'I HISOBI VA UNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	914
<i>Sh.M.Ergashev</i>	
HUDUDLARDA QURILISH OBYEKTLARINI QURILISH MATERIALLARI BILAN TA'MINLASH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	918
<i>Najimov Iskander Perdebayevich</i>	
TOVAR MODDIY ZAXIRALAR AUDITIDA TAHLILY AMALLARNI O'TKAZISH VA ULARNING BOSQICHLARI.....	922
<i>Tajekeev Ziyatdin Kobeytinovich</i>	
МЕТОДИЧЕСКИЕ ПОДХОДЫ К УПРАВЛЕНИЮ ЗАТРАТАМИ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯ В СИСТЕМЕ УПРАВЛЕНЧЕСКОГО УЧЕТА	927
<i>Минутдинова Лилия Тагировна</i>	
МОДЕРНИЗАЦИЯ ОСВЕЩЕНИЯ САЛОНОВ ВАГОНОВ МЕТРОПОЛИТЕНА ПУТЕМ ЗАМЕНЫ ЛАМП НАКАЛИВАНИЯ ЛБ-40 (ЛБ-36) НА СВЕТОДИОДНЫЕ LED-ЛАМПЫ	934
<i>Файзуллаев Асомитдин Аловитдинович, Нематов Эркин Хамраевич, Пирназаров Шохрух Холмурод угли</i>	
HUDUDYIY BARQAROR O'SISHDA INKLYUZIV IQTISODIY MEKANIZMLARNING ROLI	939
<i>Xamroqulov M.J.</i>	
UZBEKISTAN'S HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM STRENGTHENS ITS POSITION ON THE INTERNATIONAL STAGE.....	944
<i>Umarov Diyor Ravshanovich</i>	

UZBEKISTAN'S HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM STRENGTHENS ITS POSITION ON THE INTERNATIONAL STAGE

Umarov Diyor Ravshanovich

Head of international and national rankings division,
Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovations

Abstract. The higher education of Uzbekistan is undergoing a transformative phase grounded in strategic reforms towards enhancing international recognition, quality of studies, and institutional autonomy. The country's initiatives towards positioning its universities based on global best practices have resulted in increased foreign student admissions, expansion of universities, and participation in worldwide rankings such as QS and THE. One of the key factors of this development is the decentralization of higher education governance, which has granted universities increased academic and financial independence, enabling them to form closer international linkages, access foreign capital, and improve the quality of education.

Besides, Uzbekistan is carrying out the merger of universities to make the most of resources, consolidate research potential, and ensure international competitiveness, building its methods on successful experience in France and South Korea. Furthermore, the nation is emerging as a centre of higher education in Central Asia by actively engaging in international scientific forums, summits, and educational exhibitions. These efforts not only strengthen Uzbekistan's brand of education but also help foster academic diplomacy and international knowledge exchange.

While Uzbekistan has made great strides, in order to maintain this momentum, the policy further needs to be refined, more investment in research and innovation needs to be made, and institutional independence enhanced. With challenges being resolved and opportunities emerging on the horizon, Uzbekistan will be a highly regarded regional and international leader in higher education.

Keywords: Higher education reform in Uzbekistan, university rankings, academic autonomy, financial autonomy, international collaboration, university consolidation, decentralisation, Central Asia, research and innovation.

Annotatsiya. O'zbekistonda oliy ta'lim tizimi xalqaro e'tirofni oshirish, ta'lim sifati va institusional mustaqillikni kuchaytirishga qaratilgan strategik islohotlar asosida jadal transformatsiya bosqichini boshdan kechirmoqda. Jahon ilg'or tajribalariga moslashish yo'lida amalga oshirilayotgan tashabbuslar xorijiy talabalar sonining ko'payishiga, oliy ta'lim muassasalarining kengayishi va birlashuviga, shuningdek, QS va THE kabi nufuzli xalqaro reytinglarda ishtirok etishga zamin yaratdi. Ushbu jarayonning muhim omillaridan biri oliy ta'lim boshqaruvida desentralizatsiyaning kuchaytirilishi bo'lib, bu universitetlarga akademik va moliyaviy mustaqillik berib, xalqaro hamkorlikni rivojlantirish, xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb qilish hamda ta'lim sifatini oshirish imkonini bermoqda.

Bundan tashqari, O'zbekistonda resurslardan samarali foydalanish, ilmiy salohiyatni birlashtirish va xalqaro raqobatbardoshlikni oshirish maqsadida oliy ta'lim muassasalarini birlashtirish jarayonlari amalga oshirilmoqda. Ushbu yondashuv Fransiya va Janubiy Koreya kabi davlatlarning muvaffaqiyatli tajribalariga asoslanadi. Shuningdek, mamlakat Markaziy Osiyoda oliy ta'lim markaziga aylanish yo'lida xalqaro ilmiy forumlar, sammitlar va ta'lim ko'rgazmalarida faol ishtirok etmoqda. Bu sa'y-harakatlar O'zbekiston oliy ta'lim brendini mustahkamlash bilan birga, akademik diplomatiya va xalqaro bilim almashinuvini rivojlantirishga xizmat qilmoqda.

Erishilgan yutuqlarga qaramay, ushbu islohotlar sur'atini saqlab qolish uchun oliy ta'lim siyosatini yanada takomillashtirish, ilmiy tadqiqotlar va innovatsiyalarga investitsiyalarni oshirish hamda institusional mustaqillikni chuqurlashtirish zarur. Mavjud muammolarni hal etish va yangi imkoniyatlardan samarali foydalanish O'zbekistonga oliy ta'lim sohasida mintaqaviy va xalqaro miqyosda yetakchi o'rinni egallash imkonini beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: O'zbekistonda oliy ta'lim islohotlari, universitet reytinglari, akademik mustaqillik, moliyaviy mustaqillik, xalqaro hamkorlik, universitetlarni birlashtirish, desentralizatsiya, Markaziy Osiyo, ilmiy tadqiqotlar va innovatsiyalar.

Аннотация. Система высшего образования Узбекистана находится на этапе глубокой трансформации, основанной на стратегических реформах, направленных на повышение международного признания, качества образования и институциональной автономии. Инициативы по приведению университетов в соответствие с мировыми стандартами способствовали росту числа иностранных студентов, расширению и объединению высших учебных заведений, а также участию страны в глобальных рейтингах университетов, таких как QS и THE. Одним из ключевых факторов этих преобразований стала децентрализация управления высшим образованием, обеспечившая университетам большую академическую и финансовую самостоятельность, что позволило укрепить международные связи, привлечь иностранный капитал и повысить качество образовательного процесса.

Кроме того, в Узбекистане реализуется политика объединения университетов с целью более эффективного использования ресурсов, консолидации научного потенциала и повышения международной конкурентоспособности, основанная на успешном опыте Франции и Южной Кореи. Страна также формируется как региональный центр высшего образования в Центральной Азии, активно участвуя в международных научных форумах, саммитах и образовательных выставках. Эти меры способствуют укреплению образовательного бренда Узбекистана, развитию академической дипломатии и международного обмена знаниями.

Несмотря на достигнутый прогресс, для сохранения положительной динамики необходимо дальнейшее совершенствование государственной политики, увеличение инвестиций в научные исследования и инновации, а также углубление институциональной автономии. Решение существующих проблем и эффективное использование новых возможностей позволят Узбекистану занять достойное место среди региональных и международных лидеров в сфере высшего образования.

Ключевые слова: реформы высшего образования в Узбекистане, рейтинги университетов, академическая автономия, финансовая автономия, международное сотрудничество, объединение университетов, децентрализация, Центральная Азия, научные исследования и инновации.

INTRODUCTION

The higher education system plays a significant role in the economic development of any nation. It acts as a source of innovation, human capital formation, and global competitiveness. In Uzbekistan, the higher education system has historically faced structural challenges, including low internationalization levels, limited academic and financial autonomy, and outdated governance models, which hindered its ability to fully contribute to the country's economic growth. Meanwhile in Kazakhstan, higher education universities have undergone radical reforms with a strong focus on academic autonomy, internationalization, and research excellence, which has led to improved global rankings and increased collaboration with leading universities worldwide. For example: in the QS World University Rankings 2025, 12 universities of Kazakhstan have secured positions within the best 1000 global universities (QS Top Universities, 2025).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Uzbekistan's population is mainly youth and there is a high demand in higher education within the country. Even though there are a big number of universities in Uzbekistan there is still need for studying abroad, including in neighboring states. It is believed that Uzbekistan has become third largest nation for students studying abroad (Mitchell, 2024). Author argues that Uzbekistan aims to improve its system by widening access to higher education, quality assurance and TNE. Khasanov (2023) believes that Uzbekistan has initiated a chain of reforms related to granting state universities a greater autonomy, which gives academic department and faculties right to make decision based on local needs and priorities.

Enrollment rate has been increasing year by year from 571,000 in 2021 to 1,167,868 in 2023 and numbers are still increasing. To meet this huge demand the number of universities increased from 77 in 2017 to more than 210 in 2024. Even though a number of new universities (both public and private) were established there is still demand for studying abroad particularly to neighbor countries (Mitchell, 2024).

Vakhobova (2024) argues that internationalization plays significant role in producing a skilled workforce, fostering innovation and attracting foreign investments. Which in turn leads to economic growth and greater integration of Uzbekistan's economy into global arena. However, Ubaydullaeva (2023) believes that despite economic and other benefits, historically Uzbekistan's higher education system was cautious about internationalization due to promotion of national ideology. Since the approach to higher education was about preserving cultural identity.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Three principal components constitute analysis of the higher education reforms in Uzbekistan. The paper critically analyses official policies, legislation, and regulatory decrees to determine their impact on the sector’s development. Data analysis is concerned with collecting and analyzing statistical indicators, such as the number of universities established in recent years, number of internationally accredited universities, global ranking entrants, which provide an unambiguous picture of trends in the system. Comparative assessment looks into the reforms in Uzbekistan based on international good practice and compiles different aspects of reforms within the country to find strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and challenges. Limitation of the methodology includes the fact that university mergers happened short period before the research. Therefore, it might be slightly early to draw a conclusion whether it was effective or not.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In recent years, Uzbekistan’s higher education system has demonstrated remarkable progress on the global stage. Uzbek universities are now actively competing in international rankings, including QS, THE, UI GreenMetric, and Webometrics. The increasing recognition and position of Uzbek universities in subject, thematic and regional rankings highlight their growing global influence. In 2025, three Uzbek universities entered global university rankings for the first time, a milestone reflecting the country’s commitment to academic excellence. The National Research University “Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers” (TIAME) secured the 469th position, National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek (NUUZ) took 721-730 place and Tashkent State Technical University took 901-950 place in the “QS World University Rankings 2026” (QS Top Universities, 2025).

Another notable achievement of 2024 was the international accreditation of 39 educational programs of universities, confirming their compliance with global education standards. These successes did not happen by chance, it is the outcome of a chain of large-scale reforms: ensuring the transparency of admission process, improving the quality of the education, and the special attention of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the education sphere. The adoption of integrated legislation has further strengthened these successes.

One of the critical factors contributing to this global recognition is decentralization within the higher education system, which grants universities financial and academic independence. This change in policy enables institutions to manage their resources more effectively, boosting innovation and adaptability to new trends within academia worldwide. Experts in higher education highlight that autonomy is critical for universities to become more globally competitive. However, decentralization of higher education is currently limited by the fact that government still fully regulates the quota allocation and selection process.

Moreover, financial freedom of Uzbek universities enabled them to invest more in marketing of their services. For instance, Uzbek universities are actively taking part in global forums and congresses, which frequently present their success through exclusive national pavilions. Apart from strengthening the educational brand of the country, these interactions provide opportunities for exchanging knowledge and good practices. Further, organizing important forums in the country indicates that Uzbekistan has become a force to be reckoned with on the regional higher education map. Participation in the prestigious events organized by QS and THE is a key in creation of positive image of Uzbek universities in global arena.

Emulated by developed nations, Uzbekistan has come on board to consolidate its universities in order to optimize resources and enhance the quality of education. An example is the consolidation of various universities across various areas into integrated institutions that are well placed to counter contemporary academic and industrial requirements (Table 1).

Table 1: Examples of university mergers in Uzbekistan

No	Newly established university	Base institution
1.	Tashkent State University of Economics	Tashkent State University of Economics
2.		Tashkent Financial Institute
3.		Fiscal Institute
4.	Bukhara State Technical University	Bukhara Engineering-Technological Institute
5.		Bukhara Institute of Natural Resources Management
6.	Namangan State Technical University	Namangan Engineering-Technological Institute
7.		Namangan Engineering-Construction Institute
8.		Namangan Institute of Textile Industry

9. 10.	Nukus State Technical University	Nukus Mining Institute under Navoi State University of Mining and Technology
		Nukus Branch of Tashkent University of Information Technologies
11. 12.	Fergana State Technical University	Fergana Polytechnic Institute
		Fergana Branch of Tashkent University of Information Technologies
13. 14. 15.	Kokand State University	Kokand State Pedagogical Institute
		Kokand Branch of Tashkent State Technical University
		Fergana Regional Branch of the Uzbekistan State Institute of Arts and Culture
16. 17. 18. 19.	Karshi State Technical University	Karshi Engineering-Economics Institute
		Karshi Institute of Irrigation and Agro-Technologies
		Karshi Branch of Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi
		Shakhrisabz Branch of Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology
20. 21.	Termiz State University of Engineering and Agro-Technologies	Termiz Institute of Engineering and Technology
		Termiz Institute of Agro-Technologies and Innovative Development.
22.	Andijan State Technical Institute	Andijan Institute of Economics and Construction
		Andijan Faculty of Tashkent Institute of Textile and Light Industry
		Andijan Machine Building Institute

The strategy is drawn from excellent models taken by nations whose university consolidation has enhanced research capability and academic performance. The successful mergers of French universities, such as the formation of Paris-Saclay University, have enhanced their global rankings, with Paris-Saclay achieving a position of 64th in the latest Times Higher Education rankings (Dixon, 2025). Similarly, South Korean universities are pursuing mergers to address declining enrollments and financial pressures, aiming to strengthen their competitiveness and sustainability (British Council, 2023).

Additionally, Uzbekistan is positioning itself as a hub for central Asian higher education. Organization of a large number of regional and international forums, conferences and other events on the territory of the republic serves as an excellent evidence for abovementioned factor. Events such as “Central Asia as the next center of higher education” as well as “Central Asia Universities Forum” co-organized with Times Higher Education is believed to be fundamental in country’s attempts in becoming regional leaders in higher education. These events have enhanced academic diplomacy, fostered knowledge exchange, and attracted world-class universities and researchers to collaborate with Uzbek institutions.

Moreover, Uzbekistan’s universities have strengthened global partnerships by participating in international forums, congresses, and academic summits. By the initiative of the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovations of Uzbekistan a dedicated national pavilion was established at major global education exhibitions organized by QS and THE ranking agencies. It is believed that it further solidifies the presence of Uzbekistan’s universities on the international stage.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Taking into consideration of all factors mentioned above we may reach the conclusion that the combination of regulatory reforms, academic autonomy, international accreditation, and global engagement has strengthened Uzbekistan’s position in the international higher education landscape. Moving forward, Uzbekistan aims to further expand global collaborations, enhance research capabilities, and continue its upward trajectory in international rankings.

The higher education sector in Uzbekistan is undergoing a period of transformation, which is supported by strategic reforms aimed at upgrading international recognition, academic quality, and institutional autonomy. The nation’s commitment to aligning its universities with international best practices has resulted in the arrival of foreign students, growth of universities, and increased ranking participation in global rankings such as QS and THE. Accreditation of study programs with success and entry of Uzbek universities into the global rankings is the result of this way.

A substantial contributor to this success is the progressive decentralization of the administration of higher education, which has freed institutions to obtain greater academic and financial autonomy. This development has empowered universities to achieve broader international co-operation, receive foreign capital, and improve teaching quality. Yet, there are still challenges, including the full attainment of autonomy, as government regulation still influences core areas such as enrollment quotas and selection.

The other crucial strategy is consolidation of universities with the aim of optimizing resources, enhancing research potential, and being competitive. With international best practice such as the French and South Korean university consolidations, Uzbekistan is aspiring to create stronger, research-oriented institutions that compete internationally.

Besides, Uzbekistan is positioning itself as a Central Asian higher education regional hub through actively hosting and participating in major academic forums, summits, and global education exhibitions. These initiatives not only are strengthening Uzbekistan's education brand but also constructing academic diplomacy and knowledge exchange with the world's leading institutions.

It is advised for the government to reduce control on enrollment quotas and selection process and continue to provide the universities with greater academic and financial autonomy. The policy change enables universities to organize selection process on their own, invest more in research and development, attract international staff and students.

Additionally, the policy on university consolidations should be continued. However, merged universities should have a clear short, middle and long-term strategies in order to maximize the impact of the reform

In conclusion, while Uzbekistan has made an amazing amount of progress, to sustain this trend requires continued improvement in policy, more investment in research and innovation, and more autonomy for universities. By seizing present challenges and surfing on rising opportunities, Uzbekistan is ready to become a respected regional and international leader in higher education.

List of used literature:

1. British Council (2023). "Declining enrolments push Korean universities to merge". Available at: <https://opportunities-insight.britishcouncil.org/short-articles/news/declining-enrolments-push-korean-universities-merge>.
2. Dixon E. (2023). "Will France's latest amalgamated university model find its soul?" Available at: <https://www.timeshighereducation.com/depth/will-frances-latest-amalgamated-university-model-find-soul>.
3. Khasanov A. (2023). Granting greater autonomy to state universities in Uzbekistan: Implications and challenges. *International Journal of Management and Economics Fundamentals*, 3(1), 45-60. Available at: <https://theusajournals.com/index.php/ijmef/article/view/1130/1093>.
4. Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Innovation of Uzbekistan (2024). Higher Education Developments in Uzbekistan. Available at: <https://gov.uz/oz/edu/news/view/13213>
5. Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Innovations of Uzbekistan. (2024). The ranking agency QS is expected to announce the 2024 asian university rankings. Available at: <https://gov.uz/en/edu/news/view/3444>. (Accessed: 15 March 2025).
6. Mitchell N. (2024). Uzbekistan becomes the third-largest nation for students studying abroad. *University World News*. Available at: <https://www.universityworldnews.com/post.php?story=20241126164516941>.
7. QS Top Universities (2025). QS World University Rankings 2026. Available at: <https://www.topuniversities.com/world-university-rankings?countries=kz>.
8. QS Top Universities (2025). QS World University Rankings 2025. Retrieved from <https://www.topuniversities.com/world-university-rankings?countries=uz>.
9. Vakhobova M.A. (2024) "The Development of Higher Education and Its Impact on The Economy and Cultural Diversity in Uzbekistan", *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*. USA, 31, pp. 23-27. Available at: <https://zienjournals.com/index.php/tjm/article/view/5225>

muhandislik

& iqtisodiyot

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir Alibekov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2025. № 12

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

"Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali 26.06.2023-yildan
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan
№S-5669245 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: №095310.

**Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahri Yunusobod
tumani 15-mavze 19-uy**

+998 93 718 40 07

<https://muhandislik-iqtisodiyot.uz/index.php/journal>

t.me/yait_2100